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Genetic Diversity of *Catharanthus Roseus* Species Based on DNA Barcodes

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Abstract

Catharanthus roseus is a medicinal plant which contains high amount of vincristine and vinblastine, two anticancer compounds. In this study, 12 *Catharanthus roseus* individuals, which collected from three provinces in Mekong delta, were evaluated for their genetic diversity. Total DNA was extracted from fresh leaves and three DNA barcodes candidates were amplified, sequenced and aligned. On the basis of phylogenetic analysis and genetic distance, three DNA markers indicated the narrow genetic relationship among *C. roseus* accessions, the difference of flower color were not reflected on phylogenetic groups. The inter-genetic distance of ITS, *matK* and *trnS-G* were high. Therefore, *C. roseus* species were authenticated from *Jussiaea repens*, another species with similar flower and leaves morphology. Such findings proposed a reliable method for identification of medicinal plants.

Keywords: *Catharanthus roseus*, DNA barcodes, genetic diversity, medicinal plants, plant identification

INTRODUCTION

Catharanthus roseus is a valuable medicinal plant which is the main source of vincristine and vinblastine, two high antitumor capacity compounds (Lichota and Gwozdziński, 2018). During hundreds of years, *C. roseus* was used as a traditional medicine for treating various diseases like ocular inflammation, diabetes and hemorrhage (Arora et al., 2010). Nowadays, the cultivation of this herb for commercial applications is ubiquitous in Spain, United States, Africa, China, Australia, India and southern of Europe. Furthermore, drugs derived from *C. roseus* were marketed in USA, Hungary, West Germany, Italy, The Netherlands, UK (Nejat et al., 2015) and the trade reached approximately 300 million USD (Makki et al., 2019). With the growth of medical demands, it is potential that *C. roseus* cultivation for pharmaceutical applications will be accelerated and the foreground of this herb is promising in near future.

From only two wild types in nature, the former with pink flowers and reddish stems and the latter with white flowers and green stems. Breeding programs created various new cultivars. These cultivars were not only divergent in flowers, but also change other traits such as height, salt tolerance, alkaloid accumulation. Such of them have been mainly distinguished by flower color, ranging from white to pink and purple blue (Edris et al., 2012).

DNA barcoding is utilization of short nuclear or organelle DNA sequences for the identification of organisms. DNA barcoding has a clear goal to identify an unknown sample utilizing pre-existing classification and not to determine patterns of relationship (Hebert et al., 2003; Kress, 2017). Another approach is the use of chloroplast/nuclear genomes which have high species discriminatin. Many chloroplast genomic regions (*rbcL*, *matK*, *trnH-psbA*, *trnL-F*, *rpl36-rps8*, ITS and 5S rRNA) have been evaluated in plant systems by- "The Consortium for the Barcode of Life Plant Working Group (CBOL)" (CBOL, 2009) Therefore in this study, we aimed to evaluate the genetic diversity of *C. roseus* using DNA markers including ITS, *matK* and *trnS-G*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant sampling

Twelve individuals of *C. roseus* were collected from medicinal farms in Phu Tan village, An Giang province and ornamental gardens in Can Tho city and Dong Thap province, Vietnam. Additionally, two samples of *Jussiaea repens* were provided from Biology Department, Can Tho University (Fig. 1).

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Figure 1. Flower characteristics of *C. roseus* (A,B,D,E) and *Jussiaea repens*(C)

Table 1: Locations and flower morphology of 14 accessions used in this study

Species	Codes	Petal color	Eye center color
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	AG1, DT1, CT1	Purple	Red
	AG2, DT2, CT2	Purple	Yellow
	AG3, DT3, CT3	White	Yellow
	AG4, DT4, CT4	White	Red
<i>Jussiaea repens</i>	HG1, HG2	White	Yellow

Remarks: AG-An Giang; CT-Can Tho; DT-Dong Thap; HG-Hau Giang

Amplification of DNA markers

Fresh leaves were sterilized by 70% ethanol and cut into tiny pieces. Samples were incubated with liquid nitrogen for 5 minutes and grind into powder stage. Total DNA was extracted followed CTAB-based protocol from Roger and Bendich (1988) with appropriate modifications. The quantity and purity of DNA were measured by Nanodrop 2000C spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, USA). DNA integrity was examined by 1% agarose electrophoresis.

Three loci including ITS region, *matK* gene and *trnS-G* spacer were amplified with 30 μ L of volume reaction. The reagents were, 15 μ L of master mix 2X (Bioline, United Kingdom), 0.4 μ M of each forward and reverse primer and DNA template. Primer sequences were listed on Table 2, amplification process was carried in C1000 thermalcycler (Bio-rad, USA) with thermal cycles in Table 3. PCR products were separated by 2% agarose electrophoresis for 45 minutes at 50V and the bands were visualized by Run-Safe stain (Cleaver Scientific, United Kingdom). Amplicons with clear bands and no nonspecific products were sent to Nam Khoa Biotechnology Corporation for sequencing.

Table 2: Nucleotide sequences of three primer pairs for amplification of ITS, *matK* and *trnS-G*

Primers	Nucleotide sequences (5'-3')
ITS	ITS1: TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG
	ITS4: TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC
<i>matK</i>	<i>matK</i> -390F: CGATCTATTCATTC AATATTTTC
	<i>matK</i> -1326R: TCTAGCACACGAAAGT CGAAGT
<i>trnS-G</i>	F: AACGGATTAGCAATCCGACGCTTTA
	R: CTTTACC ACTAAACTATAACCCGC

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Table 3: Thermal cycles for amplification of ITS region, *matK* gene and *trnS-G* spacer

Loci	Initial denaturation	30 cycles			Final extension	Storage
		Denaturation	Annealing	Extension		
ITS	95°C	95°C	55°C	72°C	72°C	10°C
	5 minutes	30 seconds	30 seconds	1 minute	7 minutes	
<i>matK</i>	94°C	94°C	50°C	72°C	72°C	
	3 minutes	30 seconds	40 seconds	1 minutes	5 minutes	
<i>trnS-G</i>	94°C	94°C	57°C	72°C	72°C	
	5 minutes	1 minutes	30 seconds	1 minute	10 minutes	

Data analysis

DNA sequences were check manually to avoid technical errors and misidentified nucleotides were verified by quality value of chromatogram. DNA barcode loci were employed in this study including nucleus Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS), maturase K gene (*matK*) *trnS-G* intergenic spacer in chloroplast genome. Such loci were extracted from the plastid complete genome sequence of *C. roseus* (KC561139.1).

The evolutionary history was inferred by using the Maximum Likelihood method and Tamura-Nei model (Tamura and Nei, 1993). The bootstrap consensus tree inferred from 1000 replicates (Felsenstein, 1985) is taken to represent the evolutionary history of the taxa analyzed (Felsenstein, 1985). Branches corresponding to partitions reproduced in less than 50% bootstrap replicates are collapsed. The percentage of replicate trees in which the associated taxa clustered together in the bootstrap test (1000 replicates) are shown next to the branches (Felsenstein, 1985). Initial tree for the heuristic search were obtained automatically by applying Neighbor-Join and BioNJ algorithms to a matrix of pairwise distances estimated using the Maximum Composite Likelihood (MCL) approach, and then selecting the topology with superior log likelihood value. This analysis involved 13 nucleotide sequences. There were a total of 906 positions in the final dataset. Evolutionary analyses were conducted in MEGA X (Kumar et al., 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**DNA barcode amplification**

Three DNA barcode candidates consisted of ITS from nuclear genome and *matK*, *trnS-G* from plastid genome illustrated sharp bands on gel background. The bands of interest were amplified successfully with unique size. In comparison to DNA ladder, amplicon size ranged between 450-650 bp (*trnS-G*), 800-900 bp (*matK*), 500-600 bp (ITS). Nonspecific bands and primer dimers were minimized. External contamination was verified by negative control sample. Similar band size of these loci was also recorded from several plant genera (Dong et al., 2012; Selvaraj et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2017; Mahadani et al., 2018)

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Figure 2. Amplicons of three DNA barcodes; trnS-G, matK and ITS on 2% agarose gel
Notes: M-hyperladder 100 bp (Bioline, England); AG-An Giang; CT-Can Tho; DT-Dong Thap; HG-Hau Giang; NC-Negative control.

ITS region analysis

Based on the ITS sequences, *C. roseus* and *J. repens* species were classified into two monophyletic groups and such two groups expressed a high genetic distance (Fig. 2). The accuracy of these branches were verified by 58% of bootstrap value. In term of intra-variation, six *C. roseus* individuals including AG2, DT4, DT3, CT2, CT1, CT4 were variable compared to the other, this branch was proved by 56% of bootstrap. On the other hand, the majority of *C. roseus* were highly similar. In case of *J. repens* branch, the genetic distance within species was visualized. Another interesting point was the independence of genetic diversity and geography as well as flower color, accessions from different locations were not in the same branches.

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Figure 3. Phylogenetic tree of *Catharanthus roseus* based on ITS sequences

matK gene analysis

Likewise, the *C. roseus* group was identified successfully from *J. repens* based on matK gene. This plastid coding gene was higher conservative compared to the noncoding region ITS (Fig.3). Such individuals were group in to two main groups, three samples AG4, DT1 and CT1 belonged to group II, which was monophyletic compared to other *C. roseus* species in Group I. Furthermore, two *J. repens* samples remained high genetic similarity, supported by 100% of bootstrap value. In group I, such two species was also monophyletic with each other. These findings revealed that matK was also a useful marker for species identification, but this gene was also not reflect the flower phenotype and geographic location.

Figure 3. Phylogenetic tree of *Catharanthus roseus* based on matK sequences

trnS-G sequences analysis

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The correlation between three DNA markers was some of *C. roseus* samples were group in a different branch, reflecting the variation within species. This plastid noncoding spacer also discriminated 2 species into different branches, verifying by 100% of bootstrap value (Fig. 4). Furthermore, accessions in each species remained the close genetic relatedness because of narrow genetic distance.

Figure 4. Phylogenetic tree of *Catharanthus roseus* based on trnS-G sequences

Therefore, species delineation of *C. roseus* was confirmed for all three DNA barcode loci. This medicinal plant was separated completely from *J. repens*, a different species with similar flower and leaves morphology. The branches were reliable because of high percent of bootstrap value. However, the appearance of intra-variation on ITS sequence might lead to the inaccurate authentication within species. Therefore, trnS-G and matK were promising markers, which satisfying both tree-based and genetic distance approach.

The *C. roseus* full chromosome complement of $2n=16$, nuclear genome analysis of *C. roseus* was estimated to be $1C=0.76$ pg, corresponding to 738 Mbp (Guimaraes et al., 2012). Mahadani et al. (2013) suggested that matK gene showed reliable amplification, alignment, and species discrimination, so this sequence could be useful in accurate species identification for medicinal plants of Rauvolfioideae. Data from Saadedin (2018) showed that genetic similarity between twelve Iraq *C. roseus* cultivars ranged between 69% - 100%. The dendrogram constructed on the basis of RAPD band illustrated that the Iraqi cultivar was isolated from the rest eleven cultivars. Based on morphological and anatomical characteristics, and chlorophyll contents, the findings showed that *C. roseus* in Banyumas Regency (Indonesia) were separated into eight cultivars (Naipospos and Palupi, 2019). El-Domyati et al. (2012) evaluated three PCR-based markers such as RAPD, ISSR and AFLP, for eight *C. roseus* cultivars for flower phenotype as potential markers for high levels of VC and VB. A number of 79 cultivar-specific markers were determined across type of marker. Other 100 markers for important flower characteristics were also detected. They are white petal, colored petal, pink petal, petal white center and yellow flower eye center. Ibrahim et al. (2014) investigated the phylogenetic relationships among five selected species of Apocynaceae collected from various provinces of Pakistan by rps11 gene. In general, phylogenetic analysis indicated a narrow genetic background (0.5%) among target species. *Nerium oleander*, *Rhazya stricta* and *Vinca major* were significant similar, supported with a bootstrap value of 24-44 % while *C. roseus* and *Nerium oleander* showed distance relationship.

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